

THE CONQUEST OF CONQUESTS: THE ISLAMIC DISCOURSE REGARDING THE RECONQUEST OF JERUSALEM (1099-1187)

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ABSTRACT

The conquest of Jerusalem by the Crusaders was a harsh and unexpected blow to the Islamic community, a calamity that immediately generated reactions ranging from grieving, to providentialism and calls for *jihād*. The purpose of this article is to briefly examine the discourse regarding the reconquest of Jerusalem articulated after the fall of al-Quds until its recovery by Saladin in 1187. I will also look at how these discursive strategies intertwine with other phenomena, such as the re-sacralization of Jerusalem and the Holy Land, *jihād*, and the process known as the “Sunni Revival”. Likewise, special attention will be paid to the eschatological dimension that these reconquest-related lines of discourse featured.

KEYWORDS

Jihād, Jerusalem, Resurrection, Eschatology, Reconquest.

CAPITALIA VERBA

Gihād, Hierusalem, Resurrectio, Eschatologia, Restauratio.

1. Introduction¹

On June 7, 1099, the crusaders' army camped in front of Jerusalem, a city in Fatimid hands at that time.² The narrative of the conquest of the holy city as the culmination of the First Crusade recounted by most Muslim chroniclers,³ popularized and made hegemonic by Ibn al-Athīr,⁴ has three main elements: the great massacre of 70,000 or more Muslims,⁵ the looting of al-Aqsā and the Dome of the Rock, and the appeal for help from Baghdad. In some chronicles details are added, such as the burning by the crusaders of the synagogue with Jews inside, or the destruction of numerous Qur'ans.⁶

What we know for certain is that, after breaching the walls and besieging the citadel for several days, the Crusaders reached an agreement with the Fatimid garrison, allowing them to proceed to Ashkelon. Scenes of panic most likely ensued in the streets of Jerusalem as the raiders killed a good number of its inhabitants and engaged in acts of looting. Many Muslims took refuge in the Ḥaram, where they were killed despite having reached an agreement with Tancred (1075-1112), who had promised them their freedom.⁷ Thus, on July 15, 1099, the holy city of Jerusalem was taken by the Christian army, thereby achieving the Crusade's objective.

1. This article is part of a research project entitled "Violencia religiosa en la Edad Media peninsular: guerra, discurso apologético y relato historiográfico (ss. X-XV)". (Religious Violence in the Middle Ages on the Peninsula: War, Apologetic Discourse and Historiographic Narrative R&D (10th-15th centuries)" (HAR2016-74968-P), financed by the Ministerio de Economía, Industria y Competitividad (Spain). I would like to thank the editors of this special issue for inviting me to contribute to it.

2. They had conquered it from the Seljuks a year earlier. In this sense, some Sunni authors spread an alleged conspiracy between Shiites and crusaders that would explain the success of the first Crusade. See: Maher, Abu-Munshar. "Fāṭimids, Crusaders and the Fall of Islamic Jerusalem: Foes or Allies?". *Al-Masaq. Journal of the Medieval Mediterranean*, 22/1 (2010): 45-56.

3. This discursive tradition has its origins in Iraqi historians such as Ibn al-Jawzī (d. 1201). Chevedden, Paul. "The Islamic Interpretation of the Crusade: A New (Old) Paradigm for Understanding the Crusades." *Der Islam*, 83 (2006): 90-136; Hirschler, Konrad. "The Jerusalem Conquest of 492/1099 in the Medieval Arabic Historiography of the Crusades: From Regional Plurality to Islamic Narrative". *Crusades*, 13 (2014): 37-76. See also Hillenbrand, Carole. "The First Crusade: the Muslim perspective", *The First Crusade: Origins and Impact*, Jonathan Phillips, ed. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1997: 130-141; Hillenbrand, Carole. *The Crusades. Islamic Perspectives*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 1999: 64 and following; Christie, Niall. *Muslims and crusaders. Christianity's wars in the Middle East, 1095-1382*. London - New York: Routledge, 2014: 18; Cobb, Paul. *The Race for Paradise: an Islamic History of the Crusades*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014: 100 and following.

4. Ibn al-Athīr. *Al-Kāmil fī l-Ta'rikh*, ed. Muḥammad Yūsuf al-Diqāqa. Beirut: Dār al-kutub al'ilmiyya, 2003: IX, 19 and following. Translation in Ibn al-Athīr. *The Chronicle of Ibn Al-Athir for the Crusading Period from Al-Kamil Fi'l-tarikh*, trans. Donald S. Richards. Aldershot: Ashgate, 2010: I: 21-22.

5. Obviously this data is inflated, as at the time of the Crusade's conquest of the city it must have had some 20,000-30,000 inhabitants. Prawer, Joshua. *The Crusaders Kingdom: European Colonialism in the Middle Ages*. London: Phoenix, 2001: 1-16.

6. Al-'Azīmī. "La Chronique abrégée d'Al-Azimi". *Journal Asiatique*, 230 (1938): 373; Ibn Muyassar. *Akhbār Miṣr*, ed. Henri Massé. Cairo: l'Institut Francais d'Archeologie, 1919: 39.

7. Cobb, Paul. *The Race for Paradise...: 101*.

The purpose of this article, in line with the special issue's central theme, is to briefly examine the discourse related to the recovery of Jerusalem expressed after the fall of al-Quds until its reconquest by Saladin in 1187. I will also look at how these discursive strategies intertwine with other phenomena, such as the re-sacralization of Jerusalem and the Holy Land, the language of *jihād*, and the process known – in contrast to the rise that Shiism had in previous centuries, especially as a result of the creation of the Fatimid caliphate – as the “Sunni Revival”.

2. The sacredness of Jerusalem and the Holy Land

The roots of the holiness of Jerusalem, al-Quds, in Islam can be traced back to two types of references that appear in the Qur'an. The first of these, al-Arḍ al-Muqaddasa, the Holy Land,⁸ links the Palestinian region and the city to the preceding Judeo-Christian tradition. In this regard it should also be added that Jerusalem was the first *qibla* for Muslims; that is, it was the first direction towards which they prayed, before Mecca.⁹ The second reference in the Qur'an, al-Masjid al-Aqṣā, connects directly this location to the last great monotheistic religion: Islam. Included in one of the best-known Qur'anic verses,¹⁰ this last denomination, the “Farthest Mosque”, was interpreted since Umayyad times as referring to Jerusalem in the context of the night-time journey of the Prophet Muḥammad from Mecca (al-Masjid al-Ḥarām, the “Sacred Mosque”) and his ascension into heaven.¹¹ Muḥammad and his mission are legitimized in this account through the relationship established with previous prophets and the history of monotheism, and Jerusalem was characterized as one of the most important cities in Islam's sacred geography.

One type of work primarily contributed to the generation of the image of Jerusalem in Islam. I am referring to *Faḍā'il al-Quds*, or “Merits of Jerusalem”, a type of text relating the different ways a pilgrim could benefit from his visit to the

8. Q. 5: 20-24.

9. Mourad, Suleiman A. “The Symbolism of Jerusalem in Early Islam”, *Jerusalem: Idea and Reality*, Tamar Mayer, Suleiman A. Mourad, eds. Abingdon: Routledge, 2008: 86-102.

10. Q. 17: 1.

11. Dajani-Shakeel, Hadia. “Al-Quds: Jerusalem in the Consciousness of the Counter-crusader”. *The Meeting of Two Worlds*. Kalamazoo: V. P. Goss, 1986: 201-221; Elad, Amikam. *Medieval Jerusalem & Islamic Worship. Holy Places, Ceremonies, Pilgrimage*. Leiden: Brill, 1995: 28; Duri, Abdul Aziz. “Jerusalem in the Early Islamic Period 7th-11th Centuries AD”, *Jerusalem in History*, Kamil Asali, ed. New York: Olive Branch Press, 2000: 105-129. These episodes are known in Islamic tradition as *Isrā'* and *Mi'rāj*. On them, see: Blochet, Edgar. “L'ascension au ciel du prophète Mohammed”. *Revue de l'histoire des religions*, 40 (1899): 1-25 and 203-236; Porter, James R. “Muhammad's Journey to Heaven”. *Numen*, 21 (1974): 64-80; Bencheikh, Jamel-Eddine. *Le Voyage nocturne de Mahomet*. Paris: Imprimerie Nationale, 1988; Vuckovic, Brooke O. *Heavenly Journeys, Earthly Concerns. The legacy of the Mi'raj in the Formation of Islam*. New York: Routledge, 2005; Neuwirth, Angelika. “The Spiritual Meaning of Jerusalem in Islam”, *City of the Great King: Jerusalem from David to the Present*, Nitza Rosovsky, ed. Cambridge - London: Harvard University Press, 1996: 93-116.

holy city.¹² Within this genre, the *Faḍā'il Bayt al-Maqdis* by al-Walīd b. Ḥammād al-Ramlī (d. 912), the *Faḍā'il al-Bayt al-Muqaddas* by Abū Bakr al-Wāsiṭī (d. 1019)¹³ and the *Faḍā'il Bayt al-Maqdis wa-l-Khalīl wa-Faḍā'il al-Shām* by Abū al-Ma'ālī Ibn al-Murajjā (d. after 1047) stand out.¹⁴ This last work, as its title indicates, also includes materials on Hebron and the Levant. As will be seen later, this genre was very important in counter-Crusade ideology.

The importance of Jerusalem in the Islamic tradition also has to do with its eschatological role as the place where the Resurrection was to take place.¹⁵ Nāṣir-i Khusraw's account of his time in Jerusalem in 1047, describes this eschatological role of al-Quds, as well as people's perception on it:

a large, expansive, and flat plain called Sāhira. They say that this is where the Resurrection will take place, where all people will be gathered together. For this reason, many people have come there from all over the world and taken up residence in order to die in that city. When God's appointed time comes, they will already be in the stipulated place.¹⁶

The term *sāhira* appears in the Qur'an, 79:14, referring to the place of Judgment. Similarly, Al-Muqaddasī (d. 991), in his *Aḥsan al-taqāsīm fī ma'rifat al-aqālīm*, describes Jerusalem in a way that emphasizes its eschatological significance. The cities of Mecca and Medina occupy a special place through Jerusalem and its position on the Last Day:

As for the excellence of the city, is it not indeed to be the plain of the Resurrection, and the marshalling place on the Day of Judgement for the risen dead? Now it is true that Mecca and Medina are in the ascendant with the Ka'ba and the Prophet – God's peace and blessings be upon him – but truly, on the Day of Resurrection,

12. See: Sivan, Emmanuel. "The Beginning of the Faḍā'il al-Quds Literature". *Israel Oriental Studies*, 1 (1971): 263-271; Hasson, Isaac. "Muslim Literature in Praise of Jerusalem: Faḍā'il Bayt al-Maqdis", *The Jerusalem Cathedra: Studies in the History, Archaeology, Geography and Ethnography of the Land of Israel*, Lee Levine, ed. Jerusalem: Yad Izhaq Ben-Zvi Institute and Wayne State University Press, 1981: 168-184; Elad, Amikam. *Medieval Jerusalem...: 6 and following*; Mourad, Suleiman A. "The Symbolism...": 86-102.

13. Al-Wāsiṭī. *Faḍā'il al-Bayt al-Muqaddas*, ed. Isaac Hasson. Jerusalem: The Magnes Press, 1979.

14. Ibn al-Murajjā. *Faḍā'il Bayt al-Maqdis wa al-Khalīl wa-Faḍā'il al-Shām*, ed. Ofer Livne-Kafri. Shafā' Amr: Dār al-Mashriq, 1995.

15. Livne-Kafri, Ofer. "The Muslim Traditions 'In Praise of Jerusalem' (Faḍā'il Al Quds): Diversity and Complexity". *Annali*, 58 (1998): 165-192; Livne-Kafri, Ofer. "Jerusalem in Early Islam: The Eschatological Aspect". *Arabica*, 53 (2006): 382-403; Livne-Kafri, Ofer. "Jerusalem: The Navel of the Earth in Muslim Tradition". *Der Islam*, 84/1 (2008): 46-72.

16. Nāṣir-i Khusraw. *Naser-e Khosraw's Book of Travels (Safarnama); a Parallel Persian-English Text*, ed. and trans. Wheeler M. Thackston Jr. Costa Mesa: Mazda Publishers, 2001: 28. Bloom, Jonathan. "Nāṣir Khusraw's Description of Jerusalem". *No Tapping around Philology. A Festschrift in Honor of Wheeler McIntosh Thackston Jr.'s 70th Birthday*, Alireza Korangy, Daniel J. Sheffield, eds. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2014: 395-406.

they will both hasten to Jerusalem, and the excellence of all of them will be encompassed there together.¹⁷

It is important to keep in mind this eschatological role of Jerusalem in the Islamic tradition, as it was widely used, recontextualized and transformed in the Muslim discourse on the reconquest of al-Quds.

With the arrival of the crusaders, Islam not only lost the sanctity of Jerusalem, but many other sacred places in the Syrian-Palestinian region were threatened too.¹⁸ In Hebron, known in Arabic as al-Khalīl (the “friend [of God]”), there were numerous tombs of patriarchs, including that of Abraham (to which its name refers to).¹⁹ Likewise, in Halhul, near Hebron, was also Jonah’s tomb. This sacred land, moreover, was dynamic and alive, not only through commemoration rituals. In 1043-1044, for example, a piece of the skull of Yaḥyā b. Zakariyyā (John the Baptist) was found, which was preserved in the mosque of the Aleppo citadel.²⁰

Jerusalem, al-Quds, and the Syrian-Palestinian region, thus, occupied a special place in Islam’s collective imagination. Therefore, it is not difficult to imagine the feeling of sadness and helplessness that afflicted many Muslims when the Crusaders marauded through it, wreaking havoc on the holy city.

3. Lamentation and providentialism

The loss of Jerusalem definitely cut deep into the Muslims’ collective imagination and religious sensibilities, immediately after the conquest and especially in religious and intellectual circles, as calls were voiced for the defence of the territory, an ideological reaction endorsing *jihād*.²¹ This feeling of defeat and loss, together with the Muslim’s sense of impotence upon beholding their authorities’ inaction in the face of the invasion,²² is expressed very well by figures like the poet Ibn al-

17. Al-Muqaddasī, *Aḥsan al-taqāsīm fī ma’rifat al-aqālīm* (*The Best Divisions for Knowledge of the Regions*), trans. Basil Anthony Collins. Reading: Garnet Publishing, 1994, 152.

18. See: Al-Harawī. *Kitāb al-Ishārāt ilā Ma’rifat al-Ziyārāt. A Lonely Wayfarer’s Guide to Pilgrimage*, ed. Josef Meri. Princeton: Darwin Press, 2004; Talmon-Heller, Daniella. “Graves, Relics and Sanctuaries: The Evolution of Syrian Sacred Topography (Eleventh-Thirteenth Centuries)”. *Aram*, 19 (2007): 601-620.

19. Elad, Amikam. *Medieval Jerusalem...*: 21-62.

20. Sourdél-Thomine, Janine. “Les anciens lieux de pèlerinage damascaines d’après les sources arabes”. *Bulletin d’études orientales*, 14 (1952-1954): 65-85.

21. See, for example, Elisséeff, Nikita. “The reaction of the Syrian Muslims after the foundation of the first Latin Kingdom of Jerusalem”, *Crusaders and Muslims in Twelfth-Century Syria*, Maya Shatzmiller, ed. Leiden: Brill, 1993: 162-172; Hillenbrand, Carole. *The Crusades...*; Christie, Niall. *Muslims and crusaders...*; Cobb, Paul. *The Race for Paradise...*; Mallet, Alex. *Popular Muslim Reactions to the Franks in the Levant, 1097-1291*. London: Ashgate, 2014; Albarrán, Javier. *El sueño de al-Quds. Los musulmanes frente a la conquista cruzada de Jerusalén*. Madrid: La Ergástula, 2017.

22. The already mentioned requests to Baghdad for intervention against the crusaders are also an example of this.

Khayyāt (d. 1123-4),²³ whose verses seem to seek a reaction from the *umma*, and an exhortation to *jihād*.²⁴

Likewise, the loss of Jerusalem prompted a proliferation of providentialist discourse that attributed different disasters to the city's fall. For example, the Egyptian Ibn Ruzzik (d. 1160) put the earthquake of 1153 in Syria down to divine punishment, and spoke in the following terms of the abandonment of al-Quds:

This [the earthquake] is because Islam has lost Jerusalem, the centre of revelation before the descent of God's messenger... Pigs and the wine dwell in it, and the cross and the bell reign there. If Christ saw it, he would not tolerate the deeds and sayings that they [the Crusaders] attribute to him.²⁵

The fall of al-Quds was, therefore, punished by God. In addition, the loss of Jerusalem itself was understood as a divine punishment. This is clear in the *Kitāb al-Jihād* by the Damascene 'Alī ibn Ṭāhīr al-Sulamī (d. 1106), written in 1105.²⁶

In al-Sulamī's work, the first treatise on the "holy war" written after the arrival of the Western armies, the Christians' attacks are conceptualized as divine punishment to get believers back on the right path. The Damascene believed that it was all part of a greater religious and moral decline among the Muslims, the result of Islam's fragmentation, which had emboldened Allāh's enemies to attack Muslim territories.²⁷

Shortly before the Crusader's arrival this need to morally rearm, due to an alleged Muslims' laxity, had already been stressed by Abū Ḥāmid al-Ghazālī (d. 1111), credited with the revival of a new "Sunnism" that focused on recovering the spirit of the inner *jihād*.²⁸ Al-Ghazālī wrote his masterful *Ihyā' 'ulūm al-dīn* ("The Revival of Religious Sciences") in an attempt to inspire a religious awakening in a population that had succumbed to spiritual laxity. This process, which continued throughout the 12th century, came to be known as the "Sunni Revival".²⁹ This idea

23. Dajani-Shakeel, Hadia. "Jihad in Twelfth-Century Arabic Poetry". *Muslim World*, 66 (1976): 96-113; Hillenbrand, Carole. "Jihad Poetry in the Age of the Crusades", *Crusades – Medieval Worlds in Conflict*, Thomas Madden, James Naus, Vincent Ryan, eds. Aldershot: Ashgate, 2010: 9-23; Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge of the Poets Sword: Muslim Poetic Responses to the Crusades*. Leiden: Brill, 2017: 67 and following.

24. Ibn al-Khayyāt. *Dīwān*, ed. Mardam Bek. Damascus: al-Jama' al-'Ilmī al-'Arabī, 1958: 184.

25. Ibn Ruzzik. *Dīwān Ṭalā'ī' Ibn Ruzzik*. Najaf: al-Maktaba al-Ahliyya, 1964: 63. See also Dajani-Shakeel, Hadia. "Jihad in Twelfth-Century...": 96-113.

26. Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād of 'Alī ibn Ṭāhīr al-Sulamī (d. 1106): Text, Translation and Commentary*, ed. and trans. Niall Christie. Aldershot: Ashgate, 2015.

27. Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād...: 42-43*.

28. See, for example, Griffel, Frank. *Al-Ghazālī's Philosophical Theology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009; Frank, Richard. *Al-Ghazālī and the Ash'arite School*. London: Duke University Press, 1994; Garden, Kenneth. *The First Islamic Reviver: Abū Ḥāmid Al-Ghazālī and His Revival of the Religious Sciences*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014.

29. Makdisi, George. "The Sunni Revival", *Islamic Civilization 950-1150*, Donald S. Richards, ed. Oxford: Cassirer, 1973: 155-168; Safi, Omid. *The Politics of Knowledge in Premodern Islam*. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2006; Azzam, Abdel Rahman. "Sources of the Sunni Revival: Nizam u-Mulk and the Nizamiyya: An 11th-Century Response to Sectarianism". *The Muslim World*, 106/1 (2016): 97-108;

was coupled with a reaffirmation of the *jihād* of the sword due to the Crusaders' arrival.³⁰

In addition, one more circumstance must be added. The new Islamic century, which began on the first of Muḥarram, in the year 500 of the Hijra (September 2, 1106), was anticipated with anxiety and fear, sensations intensified due to the fall of Jerusalem. The Syrian chronicler al-ʿAzīmī (d. circa 1161) notes that when the Crusaders first appeared in 489 of the Hijra (1096), "Saturn was in Virgo".³¹ In the medieval Islamic astrological tradition, Saturn was a harbinger of disaster and devastation.³² Therefore, the atmosphere in the Islamic world must have been charged with a sense of doom, apocalypticism and millennialism.

4. Al-Sulamī and victory in an eschatological future

Al-Sulamī, however, was also convinced of an ultimate Islamic victory, which he expresses in a series of eschatological passages represented through several hadiths – which, as Goudie has shown, already appear in earlier works such as texts like the *faḍāʾil al-Shām*, *faḍāʾil al-Quds*, or eschatological ones –³³ like this:³⁴

The Messenger of God, may God bless him, said, "A company of my community of Muslims will not cease to conquer the enemies of God, conquering for the truth. Whoever opposes them will not harm them, nor will any of their hardships, like despair over food, until the time of God's power comes, and they are thus fated". It was asked, "O Messenger of God, where are they?" He replied, "They are in Jerusalem and its surroundings".³⁵

Griffel, Frank. "Sunni Revival", *Medieval Islamic Civilization: An Encyclopedia*, Josef Meri, ed. New York - London: Routledge, 2006: 782-783; Tabbaa, Yasser. *The Transformation of Islamic Art during the Sunni Revival*. Seattle: University of Washington Press, 2001; Berkey, Jonathan P. *The Formation of Islam: Religion and Society in the Near East, 600-1800*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003: 189-202.

30. Hillenbrand, Carole. *The Crusades...*; Albarrán, Javier. *El sueño de al-Quds...*; Goudie, Kenneth. *Reinventing jihād: jihād ideology from the conquest of Jerusalem to the end of the Ayyūbids (c. 492/1099-647/1249)*. Leiden: Brill, 2019.

31. Al-ʿAzīmī. "La Chronique abrégée...": 371.

32. Hillenbrand, Carole. *The Crusades...*: 37; Saliba, George. "The role of the astrologer in medieval Islamic society". *Bulletin D'études Orientales*, 44 (1992): 45-67. An example of this issue is found in al-Andalus. In the year 397 (September 1006 - September 1007) – a time close, therefore, to another turn of the century in the Hegira calendar – astrologers predicted the fall of the ʿAmirid dynasty due to the conjunction of the planets, in which Saturn had preponderance. Ibn ʿIdhārī. *Kitāb al-bayān al-mughrib fī akhbār mulūk al-Andalus wa-l-Maghrib*, ed. Evariste Lévi-Provençal. Paris: Librairie Paul Gautner, 1930: 13-15.

33. Goudie, Kenneth. *Reinventing jihad...*: 95-97.

34. For a detailed analysis of these passages, see: Christie, Niall. "Jerusalem in the *Kitāb al-Jihād* of ʿAlī ibn Ṭāhir al-Sulamī". *Medieval Encounters*, 13/2 (2007): 209-221; Goudie, Kenneth. *Reinventing jihad...*: 87 and following.

35. Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād...*: 51.

In this hadith al-Sulamī presents the idea of a group of the Muslim community who is destined to fight and triumph over the enemies of God until the time of His power; that is, until Judgment Day. In this way, he presents the Old Testament idea of the “just remnant”, already very present in the Bible with an important eschatological meaning;³⁶ it was a doctrine referring to a faithful minority of the chosen people that would prove able to guarantee its salvation once God’s wrath had been appeased. The messianic and eschatological dimension is linked to that hope. In this case, the “just remnant” is that company of believers who is found/ will be found in Jerusalem, and who will be an instrument through which God manifests his providential victory.³⁷

In another of these hadiths, very similar to the first, the eschatological geography intensifies:

The Messenger of God, may God bless him, said, ‘A company from my community of Muslims will not cease to fight at the gates of Damascus and their surroundings and at the gates of Jerusalem and their surroundings, the disappointment of those who forsake them not harming them, conquering for the truth until the Day of Resurrection’.³⁸

In this tradition the same idea of the “just remnant” appears, but, in addition to Jerusalem, Damascus is included, probably with the intention of engaging his Damascene audience and instilling in it a sense of identification. In this way, al-Sulamī offers his listeners a role in this eschatological perspective.³⁹

In the last hadith to which I shall refer to, al-Sulamī takes this eschatological discourse of struggle a step further:

We have heard in what we have heard of a sufficiently documented ḥadīth stating that the Rūm [Byzantines] will conquer Jerusalem for a set period of time, and the Muslims will gather against them, drive them out of it, kill all except a few of them, then pursue their scattered remnants to Constantinople, descend on it, and conquer it. This is confirmation, according to what was said in the ḥadīth [...] mentioned before, that if this situation is occurring during that time and if those mujāhidūn are from this conquering group, among them are those who will succeed in driving the Rūm out of Jerusalem and other parts of this country. They are the ones who will conquer Constantinople.⁴⁰

36. See, for example, Is. 10:22-23 and Is. 37:30-32.

37. The Christian discourses of reconquest also use this Biblical *topos* of the “just remnant”. One example is the depiction of Pelagius of Asturias and his soldiers in the “Reconquista” ideology. See, for example, Ayala, Carlos. “¿Reconquista o reconquistas? La legitimación de la guerra santa peninsular”. *Revista del Centro de Estudios de Granada y su Reino*, 32 (2020): 3-20.

38. Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād...*: 52.

39. Christie, Niall. “Motivating Listeners in the *Kitāb al-Jihād* of ‘Alī ibn Ṭāhir al-Sulamī”. *Crusades*, 6 (2007): 1-14.

40. Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād...*: 55.

Al-Sulamī, thus, describes Jerusalem as conquered by the Byzantines, who will later be expelled and driven back to Constantinople, which will be, in turn, besieged and taken by the Muslims in a process of victorious *jihād*. That is, the Damascene links the temporary loss of Jerusalem and that “just remnant”, fighting for God, to the future conquest of Constantinople.

Constantinople was a very important city in the Islamic imagination, coming to symbolize a bastion of Christian power whose conquest was always an aspiration. As Muslim scholars began to gather collections of hadiths, they included numerous accounts referring to the Muslim conquest of Constantinople in apocalyptic terms, describing it as a fated military victory forming part of a great Muslim expansion that would also include the conquest of Rome, a point that al-Sulamī also briefly mentions in another tradition.⁴¹ Some of these hadiths also suggested that, before the Muslims could take Constantinople, they would first have to stave off a Byzantine invasion of Islamic territory, which would include not only the conquest of Jerusalem, but also Byzantine attacks in North Africa and on the holy cities of Mecca and Medina.⁴²

Al-Sulamī, thus, sought to associate the “just remnant” (the audience he was exhorting to fight to regain lost territories) with an established and well-known tradition that would resonate in the minds of his listeners, promising his audience that if they took action against the Crusaders, they would be victorious and take Constantinople, as revealed by the traditions attributed to the Prophet Muḥammad himself. The fact that this “just remnant” was from Jerusalem suggests that the city would have already been reconquered. Indeed, in al-Sulamī’s own commentary on the first hadith quoted, he added an illustrative note: “It was mentioned in this sufficiently documented *ḥadīth* that [the conquerors for the truth] were from Jerusalem and its surroundings. In this rests proof of the city’s being destined to return to the Muslims and that such a company will be in it”.⁴³

In this way, al-Sulamī assigned new meanings, in the new context of the Crusades, to these early traditions and the role of Constantinople, linking them even more to Jerusalem and assigning the holy city a new eschatological role beyond the Resurrection:⁴⁴ its reconquest would mark the beginning of a triumphant *jihād* that would culminate with the conquest of Constantinople and the coming of the End

41. “We were with ‘Abd Allāh b. ‘Amr and were discussing the conquest of Constantinople and Rome, and which of them would be conquered first. ‘Abd Allāh called for a chest of *ṭakhm*, and *al-ṭakhm* means humanity, and said: ‘We were with the Messenger of God, writing down what he was saying, and we said: ‘Oh Messenger of God, which of the two cities will be conquered first?’ He said: ‘The City of Heraclius’. He means Constantinople”: Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād*...: 54.

42. See, for example, Bashear, Suliman. “Apocalyptic and Other Materials on Early Muslim-Byzantine Wars: A Review of Arabic Sources”. *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 1/2 (1991): 173-207; Arjomand, Saïd Amir. “Islamic Apocalypticism in the Classic Period”, *The Encyclopedia of Apocalypticism*, Bernard McGinn, ed. London: Continuum, 2000: II, 238-283; Cook, David. *Studies in Muslim Apocalyptic*. Princeton: Darwin Press, 2002; El Cheikh, Nadia Maria. *Byzantium Viewed by the Arabs*. Cambridge (Mass.): Harvard University Press, 2004.

43. Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād*...: 51; Christie, Niall. “Jerusalem in the *Kitāb al-Jihād*...”: 209-221.

44. See: Goudie, Kenneth. *Reinventing Jihad*...: 114 and following.

of Times. The creation of this victorious eschatological future characterizes the first phase of the discourse regarding the reconquest of al-Quds.

5. Zankī and Nūr al-Dīn: from an eschatological future to a hopeful present

Although some Islamic initiatives in the fight against the crusaders and for control of the Holy Land, such as the battle of Ager Sanguinis (1119),⁴⁵ can be observed, it will not be until the rise to power of *atābeg* ‘Imād al-Dīn Zankī (d. 1146), that certain winds of change began to blow,⁴⁶ influencing also the discourse of the reconquest of Jerusalem. He made use of the propaganda of *jihād* to secure and expand his dominions,⁴⁷ at least on the ideological level, as in practice there were some episodes that contradict this vision. He was, in many respects, a transitional figure, the first to have military success and an ideological certainty through which he used the rhetoric of *jihād* as the basis to construct an independent domain.⁴⁸ It seems that his primary motives were political and territorial ambitions, rather than the fight against the Crusaders,⁴⁹ although he ably exploited the struggle in his discourse so as to support his actions.

The 1144 fall of the capital of the first Crusader state, Edessa, to Zankī, undoubtedly marked a turning point in the future of the Muslims and the Holy Land.⁵⁰ Zankī arose as the awaited leader destined to expel the infidels, and this is how the chroniclers depicted him:

When Almighty God saw that the princes of the Islamic lands and the commanders of the Ḥanafī creed were not going to support the true religion, as well as their inability to defend those who believe in the One God, and the subjugation they suffered by their enemies, and the gravity of their despotism, [God] wished to establish over the Franks someone who could avenge the wickedness of their deeds, so he send him against the demons of the crossed stones to destroy and

45. See: Morton, Nicholas. *The Field of Blood: The Battle of Aleppo and the Remaking of the Medieval Middle East*. New York: Basic Books, 2018.

46. Zouache, Abbès. “Zangī, stratège averti (522/1128 à 541/1146)? Réexamen des sources latines et arabes”. *Bulletin d’Études Orientales*, 56 (2005): 13-42; El-Azhari, Taef. *Zengi and the Muslim Response to the Crusades: The Politics of Jihad*. London - New York: Routledge, 2016; Albarrán, Javier. *El sueño de al-Quds...*: 79 and following.

47. Sivan, Emmanuel. *L’Islam et la Croisade, idéologie et propagande dans les réactions musulmanes aux Croisades*. Paris: Adrien Maisonneuve, 1968: 44.

48. Cobb, Paul. *The Race for Paradise...*: 127; and Alptekin, Coskun. *The Reign of Zangi 521-541/1127-1146*. Erzurum: Atatürk University Press, 1978.

49. Christie, Niall. *Muslims and crusaders...*: 27-28.

50. See: Hillenbrand, Carole. “Abominable acts: the career of Zengi”, *The Second Crusade: Scope and Consequences*, Martin Hoch, Jonathan Phillips, eds. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2001: 111-132; Cobb, Paul. *The Race for Paradise...*: 135; El-Azhari, Taef. *Zengi and the Muslim...*: 91-111; Albarrán, Javier. *El sueño de al-Quds...*: 79 and following.; Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge...*: 82 and following.

annihilate them. [...] He [God] saw no one more capable [...] than the lord, the martyr ‘Imād al-Dīn.⁵¹

In this fragment we may observe three discursive elements that form the linchpin of the ideological construction around Zankī: it was God who chose the *atābeg* as his victorious leader; before his arrival there was only chaos, ineptitude and weakness; and he would be the only one capable of effectively facing the crusaders and leading the holy war. The texts also reflect the feeling that a new era was dawning after the conquest of Edessa. A poem composed by Ibn al-Qaysarānī (d. 1153), a poet close to Zankī who had fled the Syrian coast after the Crusaders’ conquest, describes it as the first in a series of victories that would ultimately lead to the reconquest of Jerusalem: “If the conquest of Edessa is the deep sea, then its shore is Jerusalem and the coast”.⁵²

That capture of Edessa, and subsequent events, such as the unsuccessful siege of Damascus by the Crusaders in 1148 – which indirectly initiated the unification of Syria under the power of Nūr al-Dīn (d. 1174), Zankī’s son –⁵³ were key to strengthening and energizing the discourse and ideology surrounding the recovery of al-Quds, in particular, and the Holy Land, in general. For example, and as various authors have pointed out, a renewed interest in this entire sacred space arose. For instance, *faḍā’il* books began to resurface and spread after Zankī’s victory, especially under the reign of Nūr al-Dīn,⁵⁴ at which time these works were also inserted into the process of recovering the science of the hadith, which saw historic achievements, such as the establishment in Damascus, in 1170, of the first Dār al-Ḥadīth.⁵⁵

The chroniclers who portrayed Nūr al-Dīn placed great importance on the religious dimension of his career, something absent from his father’s depictions, thus generating an image of an ideal Sunni ruler that combined perfectly with that of a *mujāhid*. An important element that helped shape this conception is, undoubtedly, the patronage that the Turkish leader offered the religious elites of Syria, as well

51. Ibn al-Athīr. *Al-Ta’rīkh al-bāhir fī l-Dawla al-Atābakīya*, ed. ‘Abd al-Qādir Aḥmad Tulaymāt. Cairo: Dār al-Kutub al-Kathīra, 1963: 33-34.

52. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *Kharīdat al-qaṣr wa-jarīdat al-‘aṣr: qism shu‘arā’ al-Shām*, ed. Shukrī Fayṣal. Damascus: Dār al-Kutub wa-l-Wathā’iq al-Qawmiyya, 1955: I, 110; translation in Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge...*: 86.

53. Phillips, Jonathan. *The Second Crusade: Extending the Frontiers of Christendom*. London - New Haven: Yale University Press, 2007.

54. See: Hasson, Isaac. “Muslim Literature...”: 168-184; Elad, Amikam. *Medieval Jerusalem...*: 6 and following; Mourad, Suleiman A. “The Symbolism...”: 86-102; Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge...*: 4 and following, 30 and following. On Nūr al-Dīn see, for example, Elisséeff, Nikita. *Nūr ad-Dīn: un grand prince musulman de Syrie au temps des Croisades*. Damascus: Institut Français de Damas, 1967; Albarrán, Javier. *El sueño de al-Quds...*: 94 and following.

55. Elisséeff, Nikita. *La Description de Damas d’ Ibn ‘Asakir*. Damascus: Institut Français de Damas, 1959: xxii-xxiii; Lindsay, James. E.; Mourad, Suleiman. *The Intensification and Reorientation of Sunni Jihad Ideology in the Crusader Period: Ibn ‘Asakir of Damascus (1105-1176) and His Age, with an Edition and Translation of Ibn Asakir’s The Forty Hadiths for Inciting Jihad*. Leiden: Brill, 2013: 47-50.

as his close personal relationship with them.⁵⁶ Furthermore, this bond ended up elevating Nūr al-Dīn to the status of the ultimate champion of *jihād*, as the ‘ulamā’ were constantly and deeply involved in his military campaigns.⁵⁷

If there is anyone who fully exemplifies the relationship between Nūr al-Dīn and the religious elites, and the Sunni project to revitalize *jihād*, it is Ibn ‘Asākir (d. 1176). As part of his Sunni and *jihād* renewal project,⁵⁸ Nūr al-Dīn asked Ibn ‘Asākir to write a compilation of forty hadiths on holy war. The work was written sometime between 1154 and 1170, the year in which the manuscript’s first colophon tells us of a public reading, a ritual indicating that the text was used as a tool for propaganda and the preaching of *jihād*.⁵⁹

Within all this phenomenon, “merits” were also written and transmitted about other Muslim cities threatened by occupation, such as Damascus, Alexandria and Cairo. For example, Ibn ‘Asākir himself wrote, in addition to a treatise on *faḍā’il al-Quds* – which was publicly recited in Damascus in 1160 –⁶⁰ one on Ashkelon, probably composed after the Crusaders’ conquest of the city in 1153.⁶¹ These *faḍā’il* writings served not only to revitalize the special place of these localities in Islamic tradition, but also to encourage the Islamic community to defend and recover these territories.

Another of the effects of the Crusaders’ arrival – along with other processes, such as the Sunni Revival itself, and the new Sunni-Shiite dialogue that was established –⁶² was the rebirth of this territory’s sanctity. In other words, a re-

56. Elisséeff, Nikita. *Nūr ad-Dīn...*: III, 735 and 750-779; Lev, Yaacob. “The Social and Economic Policies of Nūr al-Dīn (1146–1174): The Sultan of Syria”. *Der Islam*, 81/2 (2004): 218-242.

57. Albarrán, Javier. “‘He was a Muslim knight who fought for religion, not for the world’. War and religiosity in Islam: A comparative study between the Islamic east and west (12th century)”. *Al-Masaq: Journal of the Medieval Mediterranean*, 27/3 (2015): 191-206.

58. This phenomenon can also be seen in the foundation of religious institutions. See : Elisséeff, Nikita. “Les monuments de Nur al-Din, inventaire, notes archeologiques et bibliographiques”. *Bulletin d’Études Orientales*, 13 (1949-1951): 5-43; Elisséeff, Nikita. *Nūr ad-Dīn...*: III, 394-423; Tabbaa, Yasser. “Monuments with a Message: Propagation of Jihad under Nur al-Din”, *The Meeting of Two Worlds: Cultural exchange between East and West during the period of the Crusades*, Vladimir P. Goss, ed. Kalamazoo: Western Michigan University, 1986: 223-240; Tabbaa, Yasser. *The Transformation of Islamic Art...*; Rabbat, Nasser. “The Ideological Significance of the Dar al-‘Adl in the Medieval Islamic Orient”. *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 27 (1995): 3-28; Lev, Yaacob. “The Jihad of Sultan Nur al-Din of Syria (1146–1174). History and Discourse”. *Jerusalem Studies in Arabic and Islam*, 35 (2008): 227-284; Frenkel, Yehoshua. “Muslim responses to the Frankish dominion in the Near East, 1098-1291”. *The Crusades at the Near East. Cultural Histories*, Conor Kostick, ed. New York: Routledge, 2011: 27-54.

59. Lindsay, James. E; Mourad, Suleiman. *The Intensification and Reorientation...*: 53; Goudie, Kenneth. *Reinventing jihad...*: 119 and following.

60. See: Sivan, Emmanuel. *L’Islam Et La Croisade...*: 62-65; Hillenbrand, Carole. *The Crusades...*: 164-165; Goudie, Kenneth. *Reinventing jihad...*: 120 and following.

61. Lindsay, James. E.; Mourad, Suleiman. *The Intensification and Reorientation...*: 52-53; Talmon-Heller, Daniella. *Sacred Place and Sacred Time in the Medieval Islamic Middle East. A Historical Perspective*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2020.

62. See, for example, Jurado, Antonio. “The Seljuk jihād against Fatimid Shi’ism: an observation on the Sunni revival”, *Essays on Ottoman Civilization: Proceedings of the XIIth Congress of the Comité International d’Études Pré-Ottomanes et Ottomanes, Praha 1996*. Prague: Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic -

sacralization of the Holy Land took place through the Muslims' resistance.⁶³ In the first place, this phenomenon can be observed in the "rediscovery" and resignification of sacred places, such as the appearance of certain sanctuaries in Palestine, in places such as the Maqām al-Nabī Lūt (Lot) in Kafr Burayk,⁶⁴ or practices of veneration such as the *ziyāra* at the tombs of the patriarchs in Hebron, promoted in this context through, for example, the first itinerary to visit their holy sites.⁶⁵ In fact, although Abraham's tomb has already been listed as a pilgrimage site since long before, it was not until the 13th century that Hebron became known as al-Khalīl.⁶⁶ Another example is that of a footprint of the Prophet imprinted on a piece of basalt in Ḥawrān, which was transported to Damascus in the mid-12th century.⁶⁷

With the arrival of the Crusaders, there was also a certain competition for some sacred places.⁶⁸ For example, Ibn Shaddād (d. 1234) states that when Jabal Sam'ān (in northern Syria) was in the hands of the Crusaders, a large Christian crowd made pilgrimages there each spring. After Muslims regained control of the region in 1135, they began to venerate the site "twice as much as the Christians", and made it, in turn, a popular Islamic pilgrimage site.⁶⁹

Oriental Institute, 1998: 173-178; Meri, Josef. *The Cult of Saints among Muslims and Jews in Medieval Syria*. Oxford - New York: Oxford University Press, 2002; Hillenbrand, Carole. "The Shī'īs of Aleppo in the Zengid Period: Some Unexploited Textual and Epigraphic Evidence", *Difference and Dynamism in Islam. Festschrift for Heinz Halm on his 70th Birthday*, Hinrich Biesterfeldt, Verena Klemm, eds. Würzburg: Ergon Verlag, 2012: 163-179; Mulder, Stephennie. *The Shrines of the 'Alids in Medieval Syria. Sunnis, Shi'is and the Architecture of Coexistence*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2019.

63. This phenomenon also occurred in other areas where Islam was in decline due to Christian conquest processes, such as Al-Andalus. See: Albarrán, Javier. "Diferencias y similitudes entre la guerra santa peninsular y de Ultramar. Contexto islámico", *Reconquista y guerra santa en la España medieval. Ayer y hoy*, Carlos Ayala, Santiago Palacios, eds. Madrid: La Ergástula, 2021: 133-164.

64. Sharon, Moshe. *Corpus Inscriptionum Arabicorum Palaestinae*. Leiden: Brill, 1999: II, 12-151; Talmon-Heller, Daniella. "Graves, Relics...": 601-620.

65. Abū Shāma. *Kitāb al-bā'ith 'alā inkār al-bida' wa-l-ḥawāḍith*, ed. Mashhūr Salmān. Riyad: Dār al-Raya, 1990: 283-284.

66. Elad, Amikam. "Pilgrims and Pilgrimage to Hebron (al-Khalīl) During the Early Muslim Period", *Pilgrims and Travelers to the Holy Land*, Bryan F. le Beau, Menachem Mor, eds. Omaha: Creighton University Press, 1996: 21-62; Talmon-Heller, Daniella. "Graves, Relics...": 601-620. In this regard, another interesting case is the proliferation in Palestine of shrines to the prophet al-Khiḍr/al-Khaḍīr. See, for example, Meri, Josef. "Re-Appropriating Sacred Space: Medieval Jews and Muslims seeking Elijah and al-Khaḍīr". *Medieval Encounters: Jewish, Christian and Muslim Culture in Confluence and Dialogue*, 5 (1999): 237-264.

67. Mouton, Jean-Michel. "De quelques reliques conservées à Damas au Moyen Age, stratégie politique et religiosité populaire sous les Bourides". *Annales Islamologiques*, 27 (1993): 245-262.

68. It should not be forgotten that the arrival of the Crusaders also transformed the Christians' sacred sites, re-signifying and sanctifying certain places, and giving rise to new forms of veneration. See, for example, Boas, Adrian. *Crusader Archaeology. The Material Culture of the Latin East*. London: Routledge, 1999: 119 and following; 151 and following; Boas, Adrian. *Jerusalem in the Time of the Crusades. Society, Landscape and Art in the Holy City under Frankish Rule*. London: Routledge, 2001: 98 and following, 109 and following.

69. Ibn Shaddād. *Al-A'lāq al-khatīra fī dhikr 'umarā' al-Shām wa-l-Jazīra*, ed. Yaḥyā Zakariyyā' 'Abbāra. Damascus: Wizārat al-Thaqāfa, 199: I, 166; Sourdél, Dominique. "Rūḥīn, lieu de pèlerinage musulman de la Syrie du nord au XIIIe siècle". *Syria*, 30 (1953): 89-107. On this question, also see: Hamilton, Bernard. "Our Lady of Saidnaya: An Orthodox Shrine Revered by Muslims and Knights Templar at the Time of the

Another of the phenomena was the appearance of places and practices of worship linked to *jihād* and the counter-Crusade itself.⁷⁰ For example, the mausoleums of the combatants and martyrs of the holy war became sanctuaries. A paradigmatic case is that of al-Findalāwī, an elderly Maliki scholar who insisted on fighting against the army of the Second Crusade, despite his advanced age. Slain by the Crusaders outside Damascus in 1148,⁷¹ his martyrdom was glorified by chroniclers, biographers, and poets, and recorded on his tombstone. In a short time his tomb became a pilgrimage site.⁷² Places linked to the “sacred history” of *jihād* were also recontextualized and commemorated, an example being the tomb in Homs of Khālīd b. al-Walīd (d. 642), commander of the first Islamic conquests. Ibn Kathīr (d. 1373) relates an account of a Kurdish man’s visit to his tomb at the time of the Crusaders’ siege of Homs in 1149. The Kurd asked God for the same courage that Khālīd had had, after which he engaged the Crusaders, taking several of them captive.⁷³

With Nūr al-Dīn a further step was taken in the providentialism detected in the case of Zankī, and elements of a rhetoric of reconquest can be seen, represented through the realization of Jerusalem’s eschatological future. These ideas of providentialism, reconquest and apocalypticism are clearly seen in the *minbar* (pulpit) that Nūr al-Dīn ordered built for the al-Aqṣā mosque in 1168,⁷⁴ in this way explicitly introducing the idea of the effective recovery of Jerusalem into his discourse, along with all the rhetoric of *jihād* that is observed, for example, at the beginning of the inscription found on the pulpit.⁷⁵

This image is bolstered by a number of verses, also inscribed on the *minbar*, referring to the Day of Resurrection (*yawm al-qiyāma*).⁷⁶ This, would take place in Jerusalem, so these verses not only linked the pulpit and the language Nūr al-Dīn aimed to show on it with the Holy City, but also, through the eschatological allusion, underlined that the policies of Zankī’s son would culminate in the reconquest of al-Quds, which entailed a resurrection, a new uprising (*qiyāma*), and a new era for

Crusades”, *Studies in Church History 36: The Holy Land, Holy Lands and Christian History*, Robert N. Swanson, ed. Woodbridge: Boydell Press, 2000: 207-215.

70. There were also miraculous phenomena and manifestations of popular religiosity. See, for example, Frenkel, Yehoshua. “The Qur’ān versus the Cross in the Wake of the Crusade: The Social Function of Dreams and Symbols in Encounters and Conflict (Damascus, July 1148)”. *Quaderni di Studi Arabi*, 20–21 (2002–03): 105-132; Albarrán, Javier. “‘He was a Muslim knight...’: 191-206.

71. Ibn al-Athīr. *al-Kāmil*...: IX, 353. Translation in: Ibn al-Athīr. *The Chronicle*...: II, 21.

72. Talmon-Heller, Daniella. “Muslim Martyrdom and Quest for Martyrdom in the Crusading Period”. *Al-Masaq: Islam and the Medieval Mediterranean*, 14/2 (2002): 131-139; Talmon-Heller, Daniella. “Graves, Relics...”: 601-620; Albarrán, Javier. “‘He was a Muslim knight...’: 191-206; Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge*...: 61 and following.

73. Ibn Kathīr. *Al-Bidāya wa-l-Nihāya fī l-Ta’rīkh*, ed. Mu’awwad al-Mawjūd. Beirut: Maktaba al-Ma’arif, 1994: VII, 3172-3173. Translation in: Meri, Josef. *The Cult of Saints*...: 201-202.

74. Auld, Sylvia. “The minbar of Nur al-Din in context”, *Ayyubid Jerusalem: The Holy City in Context 1187-1250*, Sylvia Auld, Robert Hillenbrand, eds. London: al-Tajir Trust, 2009: 72-93.

75. Van Berchem, Max. *Matériaux pour un Corpus Inscriptionum Arabicarum: Syrie du Sud. Jérusalem “Haram”*. Cairo: L’Institut français d’archéologie orientale, 1925: 394.

76. Q. 16: 92.

Islam.⁷⁷ The pulpit was a representation of the victorious ideology that Nūr al-Dīn wished to convey, and it was thus envisioned by his contemporaries. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Īṣḫānī (d. 1201), for example, compared this *minbar*, temporarily in Aleppo until its installation in al-Aqṣā mosque by Saladin (d. 1193), with “a sword in its protective scabbard”.⁷⁸

The construction of the *minbar* for the al-Aqṣā mosque is not the only evidence that Nūr al-Dīn had a swift conquest of Jerusalem in mind, or that it was, at least, a perspective central to his discourse. Ibn al-Qaysarānī expressed the same thing:

It’s as though I feel his (Nūr al-Dīn) determination, may its edge not be blunted,
With its destination in al-Aqṣā. This matter has been decreed
And Jerusalem (al-Bayt al-Maqdis) is as good as purified.
There is no purification for it except when it runs with blood.⁷⁹

Likewise, Abū Shāma (d. 1267) recorded the text of a letter that Nūr al-Dīn apparently sent to the Caliph of Baghdad in which he conveyed the urgency of recovering Jerusalem, announcing that his main objective was to “drive out the worshipers of the cross from al-Aqṣā”.⁸⁰ Nūr al-Dīn, however, died in 1176, and it was Saladin, his representative in Egypt and the unifier of the lands of Islam around the Crusader states,⁸¹ who took this rhetoric of recovery to the next level.

6. Saladin: the arrival of the Resurrection and the dawn of a new era

As is to be expected, Jerusalem and its sacredness were central elements in Saladin’s discourse. For example, pre-battle preaching included readings from the genre of *faḍā’il al-Quds*.⁸² All this rhetoric, together with the reconquest of the city itself, led to a rise in pilgrimages to Jerusalem after 1187, and many pilgrims stopped in the city before heading on to Mecca.⁸³ And it seems clear that Saladin promised to

77. Albarrán, Javier. *El sueño de al-Quds...*: 108 and following.

78. Hillenbrand, Carole. *The Crusades...*: 156; Tabbaa, Yasser. “Monuments with a Message...”: 223-240.

79. Ibn al-Athīr. *al-Kāmil...*: IX, 370. Translation in: Ibn al-Athīr. *The Chronicle...*: II, 40.

80. Sivan, Emmanuel. *L’Islam Et La Croisade...*: 63.

81. See, for example, Ehrenkreutz, Andrew S. *Saladin*. Albany: State University of New York Press, 1962; Jackson, David; Lyons, Malcolm. *Saladin: The Politics of the Holy War*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1982; Azzam, Abdel Rahman. *Saladin: The Triumph of the Sunni Revival*. Cambridge: The Islamic Texts Society, 2009; Eddé, Anne-Marie. “Le paradis à l’ombre des sabres: discours sur le jihad à l’époque de Saladin”. *Mélanges de l’Université Saint Joseph*, 62 (2009): 325-354; Eddé, Anne-Marie. *Saladin*, Cambridge - London: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2011.

82. Dajani-Shakeel, Hadia. “Al-Quds...”: 201-221; Sivan, Emmanuel. “The Beginning...”: 263-271; Talmon-Heller, Daniella. *Islamic Piety in Medieval Syria: Mosques, Cemeteries and Sermons Under the Zangids and Ayyūbids (1146-1260)*. Leiden: Brill, 2007; Goudie, Kenneth. *Reinventing jihad...*: 164 and following.

83. Sivan, Emmanuel. *L’Islam Et La Croisade...*: 117-119.

promote the practice of combining a visit to Jerusalem with the *hajj* to Mecca.⁸⁴ For example, in the wake of the 1187 conquest, ‘Imād al-Dīn al-İṣfahānī wrote:

The people heard word of this noble victory, this great conquest, and they arrived [in Jerusalem] from all directions for the purpose of pious visitation and followed every road to [Jerusalem] and entered into the state of ritual consecration in Jerusalem in preparation for [the *hajj* to Mecca].⁸⁵

On Friday, October 2, 1187, the dream of reconquering al-Quds had come true.⁸⁶ After visiting the Dome of the Rock and al-Aqṣā, Saladin had the *minbar*, which Nūr al-Dīn had ordered to build for the famous mosque and had been kept in Aleppo, brought in. The idea spread that God had chosen Saladin to carry out this conquest, and that such had been his destiny.⁸⁷ In fact, the Andalusī mystic Ibn Barrajān (d. 1141) was said to have predicted this achievement in his commentary on verse Q. 30: 2, alluding to the defeat of the Christians.⁸⁸ The conquest was described by authors like ‘Imād al-Dīn al-İṣfahānī as the *fath al-futūḥ*, the conquest of conquests, a triumph that would surpass all other victories in Islamic history.⁸⁹ In this sense, the systematic use, in all this rhetoric, of the term *fath* by authors such as al-İṣfahānī is not accidental, but responds to the intention of presenting it as a new conquest, like the one occurring in the early days of the *umma*, a reconquest that needed a new opening to Islam, a re-Islamization.⁹⁰

84. Antrim, Zayde. “Jerusalem in Ayyubid and Mamluk periods”, *Routledge Handbook on Jerusalem*. London: Routledge, 2018: 102-109; Auld, Sylvia and Hillenbrand, Robert. *Ayyubid Jerusalem: The Holy City in Context 1187-1250*. London: al-Tajir Trust, 2009.

85. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-İṣfahānī. *Al-Fath al-Qussī fī l-fath al-Qudsī*. El Cairo: Dār al-Manār, 2004: 75. Translation in: ‘Imād al-Dīn al-İṣfahānī. *La Conquête de la Syrie et de la Palestine par Saladin*, trans. Henri Massé. Paris: Librairie Orientaliste Paul Geuthner, 1972: 48-49.

86. See, for example, Ibn al-Athīr. *al-Kāmil...: X*, 154 and following.; Translation in : Ibn al-Athīr. *The Chronicle... : II*, 330 and following. See also: Dajani-Shakeel, Hadia. “Some Medieval Accounts of Saladin’s Recovery of Jerusalem (Al-Quds)”, *Studia Palaestina: Studies in honour of Constantine K. Zurayk*, Hisham Nashabe, ed. Beirut: Institute for Palestine Studies, 1988: 83-113.

87. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-İṣfahānī. *al-Fath...: 82*. Translation in: ‘Imād al-Dīn al-İṣfahānī. *La Conquête...: 59*.

88. Bellver, José. “Ibn Barragan and Ibn Arabi on the Prediction of the Capture of Jerusalem in 583/1187 by Saladin”. *Arabica*, 61 (2014): 252-286; Ibn Barrajān. *A Qur’ān Commentary by Ibn Barrajān of Seville (d. 536/1141)*. *İdāḥ al-ḥikma bi-ahkām al-‘ibra (Wisdom Deciphered, the Unseen Discovered)*, eds. Gerhard Böwering, Yousef Casewit. Leiden: Brill, 2016: 27-29.

89. Abū Shāma. *Kitāb al-Rawḍatayn fī akhbār al-dawlatayn al-nūrīyya wa-l-ṣalāḥīyya*, ed. Ibrāhīm Shams al-Dīn. Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-‘Ilmiyya, 2002: II, 244.

90. On the concept of *fath* see: García Sanjuán, Alejandro. “La noción de *fath* en las fuentes árabes andalusíes y magrebíes (siglos VIII al XIII)”, *Orígenes y desarrollo de la Guerra Santa en la Península Ibérica: palabras e imágenes para una legitimación (siglos X-XIV)*, Carlos de Ayala, Patrick Henriet, Santiago Palacios, eds. Madrid: Casa de Velázquez, 2016: 31-50; Donner, Fred. “Arabic *Fath* as ‘Conquest’ and its Origin in Islamic Tradition”. *Al-‘Uṣūr al-Wuṣṭā*, 24 (2016): 1-14. This use of the term *fath* to highlight the need to reconquer and re-Islamize the territory can also be seen in the Islamic reconquest discourse in al-Andalus. See Albarrán, Javier. “Una reconquista de la reconquista: la reacción ideológica islámica al avance cristiano (ss. XI-XIII)”, *La Reconquista. Ideología y justificación de la guerra santa peninsular*, Carlos de Ayala, Isabel C. Fernandes, Santiago Palacios, eds. Madrid: La Ergástula: 233-257; Albarrán, Javier.

After the reconquest of al-Quds, the *shāfiʿī* preacher from Damascus Ibn al-Zakī (d. 1192) was chosen to give the victory sermon,⁹¹ describing it as a gift from God, who made “it easy for your hands to recover this strayed camel [Jerusalem] from the possession of a misguided people, and to bring it back to the fold of Islam, after it had been abused by the polytheists for nearly one hundred years”.⁹² That is, Jerusalem is described as a city that was recovered after being lost, usurped, and tainted by infidelity. This same idea is seen in al-İṣfahānī, who emphasizes the fact that the law of God had been restored in the holy city.⁹³

That is, Saladin brought restoration, renewal and revival, in the sense expressed by al-Ghazālī, to Jerusalem. The laws of religion returned to the house of God (*ʿādāt*⁹⁴ *bayt Allāh aḥkām dīni-hi*), a city that, due to the Crusaders’ conquest, had succumbed to infidelity. A poem by the Egyptian Ibn Sanā’ al-Mulk (d. 1211) reflects this idea clearly: “You gave life to it after it had died, and then you freed it after it was a captive. Gabriel yearned for his house [Bayt al-Maqdis], and his house yearned for him, so he came to it with a longing and a yearning”.⁹⁵

This motif of liberation is also very much present in the whole rhetoric of the reconquest of Jerusalem that arose around Saladin.⁹⁶ For example, ʿImād al-Dīn al-İṣfahānī composed this rhymed prose in which he once again associated the sacredness of Jerusalem with that of Mecca and Medina:

Ejércitos benditos. Yihad y memoria en al-Andalus (siglos X-XIII). Granada: Universidad de Granada, 2020: 355 and following.

91. Ibn al-Athīr. *Al-Kāmil*...: X, 158. Translation in: Ibn al-Athīr. *The Chronicle*...: II, 334.

92. Ibn Khallikān. *Kitāb Wafayāt al-aʿyān wa-anbāʾ abnāʾ al-zamān*, trans. William M. de Slane. Paris: Oriental translation fund of Great Britain and Ireland, 1843-1871: II, 635 and following.

93. Abū Shāma. *Kitāb al-Rawḍatayn*...: III, 233. On these questions, see: Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge*...: 99 and following.

94. This verb is often used in medieval Islamic chronicles referring to the providential return to Islam, especially Islamic law, of a territory that had been seized by the infidels. In the case of al-Andalus, for example, one can find several examples of it. A paradigmatic one is this fragment from *Faṭḥ al-Andalus* referring to the Almoravids’ victory at Zallāqa (1086): “In it, all the unbelievers they encountered were annihilated, and thanks to this battle God saved those who were on the Peninsula, since it had been on the verge of perishing. God, in his Grace, shall see to it that it is once again a territory of the faithful (*Allāh yaʿīdu-hā dār imān*) for as long as the day and night succeed each other”: *Faṭḥ al-Andalus*, ed. Luis Molina. Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, 1994: 120-121. On these issues, see: Albarrán, Javier. “Una reconquista...”: 233-257.

95. Ibn Sanā’ al-Mulk. *Dīwān ibn Sanāʾ al-Mulk*, ed. Muḥammad Ibrāhīm Naṣr. Cairo: Wizārat al-Thaqāfa, 1969: II, 340. Translation in Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge*...: 112.

96. This idea of “liberation” also appears in the Islamic reconquest narrative of some Andalusī cities, such as in the case of Almeria in the days of the Almohad caliph ʿAbd al-Muʿmin. Ibn Abī Zarʿ. *Kitāb al-anīs al-muṭrib rawḍ al-qirṭās fī akhbār mulūk al-Maghrib wa-taʾrīkh madīnat Fās*. Rabat: Dār al-Manṣūr, 1972: 193. Likewise, the notion of “liberation” appears frequently in the discourse of the Christian reconquest of the Iberian Peninsula and in the Crusader rhetoric. See, for example, Ayala, Carlos. “El discurso de la guerra santa en la cancillería castellana (1158-1230)”, *Orígenes y desarrollo de la Guerra Santa en la Península Ibérica: palabras e imágenes para una legitimación (siglos X-XIV)*, Carlos de Ayala, Patrick Henriot, Santiago Palacios, eds. Madrid: Casa de Velázquez, 2016: 155-185. These issues, along with others already mentioned, such as the *topos* of the “just remnant”, shows an interesting transcultural rhetoric in these ideologies of reconquest.

And Masjid al-Ḥarām was given glad tidings that al-Aqṣā has been liberated, and the Black Stone was congratulated because of the liberation of the White Rock, and the place of revelation was congratulated because of the liberation of the abode of ascent, and the abode of the leader of the messengers and the seal of the prophets was congratulated because of the liberation of the abode of messengers and prophets, and the station of Abraham was congratulated because of the liberation of the footprint of the chosen one [Muḥammad].⁹⁷

This restoration and liberation of Jerusalem was also manifested through a material purification and re-Islamization. For example, in an inscription on the Dome of the Rock it can be read: “Saladin has purged this sacred house of polytheists”.⁹⁸ Also, between 1187 and 1192 several Christian buildings in the city were converted into Islamic institutions. For example, the Church of St. Anne in northeast Jerusalem, was transformed into a Shāfiʿī school known as al-Ṣāliḥiyya.⁹⁹

And, of course, the eschatological perspective was also very present in the rhetoric of the reconquest of Jerusalem set in motion by Saladin and his circle. In fact, the conquest of al-Quds was presented as the realization of that eschatological future linked to the city previously resignified by al-Sulamī. For example, Saladin’s reconquest was described by the poet al-Jilyānī as *bāghit*; or “sudden”.¹⁰⁰ This term appears several times in the Qurʾān in reference to the arrival of the Last Day.¹⁰¹ And, in another poem by this author composed after the recovery of al-Quds, Constantinople appears again, as it did in al-Sulamī: “Hagia Sophia (Ayasūfiyā) pleads with you in remembrance of what you did in [the Church of] Resurrection (*qiyāma*). Indeed this is the conquest that will shock the entire world”.¹⁰²

This idea of the arrival of eschatological time was rounded out by a re-reading of the sacred history of Islam in the light of the reconquest of Jerusalem. Saladin’s victories were likened to the *jihād* of the Prophet and the first caliphs.¹⁰³ For example, Ibn al-Zakī, in the victory sermon after the reconquest of al-Quds, compared Saladin’s triumph to the military successes of the early days of Islam:¹⁰⁴ “You have revived for Islam the glorious days of al-Qādisiyya, the battle of Yarmūk, the siege of Khaybar, and the impetuous attacks of Khālid b. al-Walīd”.¹⁰⁵

97. Abū Shāma. *Kitāb al-Rawḍatayn*...: III, 222. Translation in Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge*...: 95-96.

98. Azzam, Abdel Rahman. *Saladin*...: 196.

99. Pahlitzsch, Johannes. “The Transformation of Latin Religious Institutions into Islamic Endowments by Saladin in Jerusalem”, *Governing the Holy City. The Interaction of Social Groups in Medieval Jerusalem*, Lorenz Korn, Johannes Pahlitzsch, eds. Wiesbaden: Reichert, 2004: 47-69.

100. Al-Jilyānī. *Dīwān al-tadbīj*, ed. Kamāl Abū Dīb. Beirut: Dār al-Sāqī, 2010: 96.

101. For example, Q. 21: 40. On this issue, see: Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge*...: 100 and following.

102. Al-Jilyānī. *Dīwān*...: 93. Translation in: Latiff, Osman. *The Cutting Edge*...: 116.

103. On the memory of Islam’s first battles, see: Albarrán, Javier. *Ejércitos benditos*... On Saladin and his relationship to the sacred history of Islam, see: Albarrán, Javier. *El sueño de al-Quds*...: 157-160.

104. This phenomenon can also be seen, more subtly, in the case of Zankī and Nūr al-Dīn. See, for example Ibn al-Athīr. *Al-Taʾrīkh*...: 34; Ibn al-Athīr. *Al-Kāmil*...: IX, 375; translation in: Ibn al-Athīr. *The Chronicle*...: II, 46.

105. Ibn Khallikān. *Kitāb Wafayāt*...: II, 635 and following.

In this regard, the conquest of Jerusalem had coincided, or had been made to coincide, with the anniversary of the Prophet's night-time journey from Mecca to Jerusalem, and his ascension to heaven, another episode replete with eschatological overtones. On this, Ibn Shaddād wrote:

The sultan received the surrender on Friday 27 Rajab [2 October]. The eve had been the [date of the] Prophetic Ascension which is written about in the Noble Qur'an. Observe this remarkable coincidence, how God facilitated its restoration to Muslim hands on the anniversary of their Prophet's Night-Journey. This is a sign that God had accepted this proffered obedience.¹⁰⁶

For his part, 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī titled his biography of Saladin *al-Barq al-Shāmī*, the "Syrian lightning bolt".¹⁰⁷ It is no coincidence that *barq* comes from the same root as *al-Burāq*, the name of the mythological animal that transported Muḥammad from Mecca to Jerusalem on that night journey.¹⁰⁸ All this gave the reconquest of al-Quds and the *jihād* that had made it possible an aura of even greater providentialism and eschatology, and at the same time, inserting it in a privileged position in the sacred history of Islam.

All these ideas are perfectly reflected in a text that should be described as definitive and authoritative on the ideology of the reconquest of Jerusalem: *al-Faṭḥ al-Qussī fī l-faṭḥ al-Qudsī* also by 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī.¹⁰⁹ The title of this work could be translated as "The inspiration of Quss¹¹⁰ concerning the conquest of Jerusalem".¹¹¹ The introduction to this work, dedicated exclusively to Saladin's reconquest of the holy city, and written by one of his closest collaborators, is anthological. The text begins by speaking of the Prophet and his companions as conquerors of the East and the West, thus establishing an implicit parallel with the era of Saladin.¹¹² It then goes on to describe the history of humanity as a succession of different phases, epochs, which arise as if they were resurrections:

106. Ibn Shaddād. *Al-Nawādir al-sultāniyya wa-l-mahāsīn al-yūsufiyya*, ed. Jamāl al-Dīn Shayyāl. Cairo: al-Dār al-Miṣriyya li-l-ta'līf wa-l-tarjama, 1964: 135; translation in: Ibn Shaddād. *The Rare and Excellent History of Saladin or al-Nawādir al-Sultāniyya wa'l-Mahāsīn al-Yūsufiyya*, trans. Donald S. Richards. Aldershot: Ashgate, 2007: 77.

107. 'Imād al-Dīn Al-Iṣfahānī. *Al-Barq al-Shāmī*. Amman: Mu'assasat 'Abd al-Hamīd Shūmān, 1987; Gibb, Hamilton A. R. "Al-Barq Al-Shāmī: The History of Saladin by the Kātib 'Imād Ad-Dīn Al-Iṣfahānī". *Wiener Zeitschrift Für Die Kunde Des Morgenlandes*, 52 (1953): 93-115; Rabbat, Nasser. "My Life with Salāh al-Dīn: The Memoirs of 'Imād al-Dīn al-Kātib al-Iṣfahānī". *Edebiyāt*, 7/2 (1996): 267-287.

108. Dajani-Shakeel, Hadia. "Al-Quds...": 201-221.

109. Richter-Bernburg, Lutz. "Observations on 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī's al-Faṭḥ al-Qussī fī l-faṭḥ al-Qudsī". *Studia Arabica et Islamica-Festschrift for Ihsan 'Abbas*, Wadād al-Qadī, ed. Beirut: American University of Beirut, 1981: 373-379.

110. Quss b. Sā'ida al-Iyādī, legendary pre-Islamic orator.

111. Al-Iṣfahānī himself explains the selection of this title in his work. 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *al-Faṭḥ...: 41*; translation in: 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête...: 11-12*.

112. 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *al-Faṭḥ...: 34-35*; translation in: 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête...: 2*.

Let man know, therefore, before ending his existence and descending into the grave, what people who deny the reality of the Resurrection (ḥaḳīqat al-nashr) find improbable; that in one of them the testimony of ten phases [of man's history] is received; that is, that humanity has passed from one era to another, from one era to another. That [humanity] was buried and then resurrected in a thousand graves.¹¹³

In this regard, it briefly mentions the history of different peoples up to the time of Islam, describing the Hijra as one of those foundational moments: "The time of the Hijra was when [...] Islam enjoyed supremacy [...] That year it had the privilege of superiority, and all the subsequent years are considered very ordinary".¹¹⁴

Immediately, al-Iṣfahānī proceeds to argue that he chose, for the beginning of this work's chronology, a second Hijra superior to that first, this being the reconquest of Jerusalem.¹¹⁵

However, I have adopted, for the beginning of my chronology, a second Hijra attesting that the end of the first will be marked by the Resurrection (bi-l-qiyaḡama) and that its promise is the true one, which we do not refute, the one that is obvious, the one that we do not falsify. This Hijra is Islam's emigration to Jerusalem (hijrat al-Islam ilā l-Bayt al-Maḡḍis). Its creator is Sultan Ṣalāḡ al-Dīn Abū l-Muḡaffar Yūsuf b. Ayyūb. It is good that the chronology is based on and coordinated in the year of this second Hijra of Islam that preceded to Jerusalem [...] By the power of God, this Hijra is the more transcendent of the two Hijras, and this return (al-karra) is the more effective of the two returns.¹¹⁶

In this last sentence, al-Iṣfahānī plays on the polysemy of the term *al-karra*, which literally means "return". Although it may mean "to overrun the enemy",¹¹⁷ it has also clearly eschatological connotations, as it makes reference to the Day of Return (*yawm al-karra*); that is, the Resurrection.¹¹⁸ Therefore, the idea of "reconquest", of an (armed) return of Islam to Jerusalem, loaded with apocalypticism and references to the last days, is being emphasized again.

And this assessment is so because, while in the first Hijra Islam was in an ascendant phase, this second Hijra took place at a time when the Islamic community

113. 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *al-Fath*...: 35; translation in: 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête*...: 3-4.

114. 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *al-Fath*...: 36-37; translation in: 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête*...: 6.

115. The Hegira features, in addition, an evident association with the idea of *jihād*. See, for example, Crone, Patricia. "The First Century Concept of Hiḡra". *Arabica*, 61 (1994): 352-387; Ebstein, Michael. "The Connection between *Hijra* and *Jihād* in Classical Islam". *Jamā'a*, 15 (2005-2006): 53-85; Lindstedt, Ilkka. "*Muhājirūn* as a Name for the First/Seventh Century Muslims". *Journal of Near Eastern Studies*, 74/1 (2015): 67-73.

116. 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *al-Fath*...: 37; translation in: 'Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête*...: 6.

117. In this sense, Henri Massé translated the term as "war".

118. See, for example, Ghaemmaghamu, Omid. "And the Earth will Shine with the Light of its Lord' (Q. 36: 69): Qā'im and qiyāma in Shi'i Islam", *Roads to paradise: eschatology and concepts of the hereafter in Islam*, Sebastian Gunther, Todd Lawson, eds. Leiden: Brill, 2017: 605-648.

had lost its greatness, was divided, and had entered into an era of moral laxity that had prompted God to punish it. And, for this reason, it was more meritorious:

Syria had been conquered at a time when Islam had declined from its greatness, when its hair had turned white, its youth was gone, its skin had wrinkled, and it felt like a stranger,¹¹⁹ as in its early days [...] Love for the incidental goods of this infraworld had rendered men blind and deaf, and the acquisition of the poor riches of this life had distracted them from the abundant bliss of the other life.¹²⁰

This situation emboldened the infidels, just as al-Sulamī had declared:¹²¹ “As for the infidels, their manners had become harsh, their dominions had been extended; they were insightful during a time of perplexity, and they prepared for battle”.¹²²

Thus, with the recovery of Jerusalem and its purification, “Islam demanded Jerusalem as a wife,¹²³ offered it the lives of the combatants as a dowry, and brought it well-being, to avoid unhappiness”.¹²⁴ There was a “clear victory”, a Qur’anic reference¹²⁵ that situated Saladin’s triumph back within the sacred history of Islam. “The century of Saladin surpasses the preceding centuries”, says al-Iṣfahānī, ushering in a new era initiated with a Resurrection, the reconquest of Jerusalem. In this way, the eschatological future augured by al-Sulamī was transformed into a new reality, a new future, marked by an event – the recovery of al-Quds – that was interpreted in an apocalyptic way. This perspective had already been suggested by Nūr al-Dīn on his *minbar*, but it would be Saladin who finally made this symbiosis of *jihād* and eschatology a reality, along with his courtiers, as ‘Imād al-Dīn himself would clearly reflect it. This is why – narrates al-Iṣfahānī – in the first sermon delivered in a purified al-Aqṣā mosque, the preacher spoke of the Resurrection.¹²⁶ The Resurrection had finally come to Jerusalem, as Islamic tradition predicted.

Providentialism and eschatology were, from the very first moment, the two elements that, in a constant and increasing way – even transforming the conquest into Resurrection –, nourished the Islamic discourse of the reconquest of Jerusalem, providing it with symbolic, sacred, historical and emotional value. Al-Quds played a fundamental eschatological role in the Islamic tradition, and inserting its recovery into that apocalyptic narrative was an effective discursive claim. In this sense, it is

119. This idea of feeling like a “stranger” also has an important apocalyptic connotation. See, for example, Fierro, Maribel. “Spiritual alienation and political activism: the *ghuraba* in al-Andalus during the sixth/twelfth century”. *Arabica*, 47/2 (2000): 230-260.

120. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *Al-Fath*...: 37; translation in ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête*...: 7.

121. Al-Sulamī. *The Book of the Jihād*...: 42-43.

122. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *Al-Fath*...: 38; translation in: ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête*...: 8.

123. This image of Jerusalem as a wife appears also in the Bible in an eschatological framework. See, for example, Rv. 21: 2. I would like to thank Carlos de Ayala for this reference.

124. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *Al-Fath*...: 66 and following; translation in: ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête*...: 44 and following.

125. Q. 48: 1.

126. ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *Al-Fath*...: 78; translation in: ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Iṣfahānī. *La Conquête*...: 53-54; Ibn Khallikān. *Kitāb Waḡayāt*...: II, 635 and following.

interesting to observe how many of these narratives were common to the Christian rhetoric of reconquest and crusade – as has been shown in this paper through cases such as that of the “just remnant” or the idea of “liberation” –, revealing a shared transcultural background that refers to the same Old Testament arsenal. In fact, the Crusade – particularly the crusader conquest of Jerusalem – was understood not only as the recovery of a lost territory, but also as a realization of the eschatological future.¹²⁷

127. See, for example, Rubenstein, Jay. *Armies of Heaven: The First Crusade and the Quest for Apocalypse*. New York: Basic Books, 2011.

